

RFID Smart Wood

Tracing wood items with embedded RFID tags

A passive UHF chip-set is embedded in wood to enable traceability of any individual item in a manufacturing process and during the lifetime of a timber product. Traceability enables digital solutions for transparent circular value chains.

Highlights of innovative features

- The RFID Smart Wood tag is designed to offset the negative components and properties when embedded in wood. It resists physical damage that may occur as a result of swelling and shrinkage.
- It solves backscatter frequency issues related to wood properties, external factors, and ageing factors.
- Registered identification contained in the RFID tag allows to record full history and use or location of any object or asset.

RFID traceability tools can bring automation in wood industries to the next level of the 'Smart factory'. The possibilities include full real time data control across the factory, warehouse management, reverse traceability of products, reverse product engineering, and thus inspection mechanisms such as certification.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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